

On the Divine Liturgy

also known as "Ἱστορία ἐκκλησιαστικὴ καὶ μυστικὴ θεωρία"

By Magdalena Garnczarska, Jagiellonian University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Text, Christian Traditions, Orthodox Christianity, Byzantine text, Orthodoxy, Byzantine liturgical commentary

Germanos' treatise "On the Divine Liturgy" has survived in numerous manuscripts and diverse versions, making it very difficult to determine the original form of the text. A significant number of manuscripts testifies primarily to the popularity of the treatise. At the same time, numerous reviews also point to the evolution of the liturgy - successive interpolations and changes in the arrangement of chapters say a lot about the transformations within the liturgy. They also prove that the treatise did not become "antiquarian" reading but remained "alive", explaining the meaning of individual liturgical rites and the objects used during them. Slightly simplifying the problem, it can be said that the text changed with the liturgy. It was Maximus the Confessor who wrote the first Byzantine liturgical commentary - "Μυσταγωγία" - which initiated a new genre that would be developed until the end of the Byzantine Empire. Thus, Germanos' "Ἱστορία ἐκκλησιαστικὴ καὶ μυστικὴ θεωρία" by Germanos is another stage in the development of Byzantine liturgical commentaries. In this text, Germanos presented the liturgy from a double perspective: the heavenly liturgy and the earthly life of Christ as well. The text in the edition prepared by Nilo Borgia contains 43 chapters of varying lengths. The narrative actually begins in medias res because any introduction does not precede it. Similarly, there is no separate conclusion or summary. Apart from these shortcomings, the commentary has a reasonably logical structure, in which we can distinguish three essential parts: 1. the first one is devoted primarily to the space of the church, gestures, liturgical vessels and vestments, as well as people serving during the liturgy (1-22); 2. the second one is on the introductory rites and the liturgy of the Word, which consists of antiphons, psalms, the First (or Little) Entrance, readings from the Apostolic Letters and the Gospels, and the Cherubic Hymn (23-35); 3. the third is on the Eucharist, consisting of the Great Entrance, anaphora, communion and sending out; in this part, the sense of the Lord's Prayer is also laid out (36-43). The author generally explains subsequent issues that form separate chapters. Thus, it is not a continuous story but rather a collection of unconnected explanations, usually closed wholes. However, their well-thought-out order - essentially corresponding to the course of the liturgy - determines the final coherence of the work so that we can talk about a treatise and not just a loose collection of instructions. The most likely author of the treatise is Patriarch Germanos I. Broadly speaking, Germanos lived from about the second half of the 7th century to the first half of the 8th century. Germanos' father was Justinian, a patrician serving at the court of Heraclius. In 668, on the orders of Constantine IV Pogonatus (668-685), he was executed for allegedly participating in a conspiracy against Constantine II (641-668), who was murdered in Syracuse. In connection with this situation, young Germanos also suffered because he was castrated. After castration, Germanos was included in the Church of Holy Wisdom clergy in Constantinople. Then he served as the Metropolitan of Cyzicus from around 705 (?). After the death of Patriarch John VI of Constantinople (711-715), Germanos was elected in his place. He resigned from office in 730. This decision was due to the conflict with the emperor Leo III (717-741), who was supposed to persuade the patriarch to adopt an iconoclastic attitude. However, it was only in texts from the beginning of the 9th century (Theophanes the Confessor's "Chronicle"; Stephen the Deacon's "Life of St. Stephen the Younger") that Germanos was portrayed as a heroic opponent of iconoclasm. Germanos I is considered the author of many texts, among which we can distinguish letters, sermons, and theological and poetic works. Some of them - like "Ἱστορία ἐκκλησιαστικὴ καὶ μυστικὴ θεωρία" - raise doubts among researchers because it is often difficult to find unambiguous evidence confirming the authorship of the holy patriarch.

Date Range: 700 CE - 730 CE

Region: Constantinople

Region tags: Byzantium, Constantinople

Constantinople, place of activity of Germanos I of Constantinople (Ecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople, 715-730 AD)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Borgia N. (ed.), "Il commentario liturgico di S. Germano patriarca Costantinopolitano e versione latina di Anastasio Bibliotecario", Grottaferrata 1912 (Studi Liturgici 1).
- Source 2: St Germanos of Constantinople, "On the Divine Liturgy", the Greek text with translation, introduction, and commentary by P. Meyendorff, Crestwood, New York 1984 (Popular Patristics Series 8), pp. 55-107.
- Source 3: Красносельцев Н.Ф. (ed. and trans.), "Сведения о некоторых литургических рукописях Ватиканской библиотеки с замечаниями о составе и особенностях богослужебных чинопоследований, в них содержащихся, и с приложениями", Казань 1885, pp. 323-375.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/ondivineliturgy1984germ/page/54/mode/2up>

–Source 2 Description: St Germanus of Constantinople, "On the Divine Liturgy", the Greek text with translation, introduction, and commentary by P. Meyendorff, Crestwood, New York 1984 (Popular Patristics Series 8), pp. 55-107.

–Source 3 URL:

<https://azbyka.ru/otechnik/books/original/13447/%D0%9A%D1%80%D0%B0%D1%81%D0%BD%D0%BE%D1%81%D0%B5%D0%BB%D1%8C%D1%81%D0%A1%D0%B2%D0%B5%D0%B4%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D1%8F%20%D0%BE%20%D0%BD%D0%B5%D0%BA%D0%BE%D1%82%201885.pdf>

–Source 3 Description: Красносельцев Н.Ф. (ed. and trans.), Сведения о некоторых литургических рукописях Ватиканской библиотеки с замечаниями о составе и особенностях богослужбных чинопоследований, в них содержащихся, и с приложениями, Казань 1885, pp. 323–375.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked
– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper
– Specify: To put it precisely, the oldest manuscripts of Germanos' text were written on parchment.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: We do not have the autograph of the text. Therefore we know nothing about possible material modification before the writing.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: "On the Divine Liturgy" ("Ἱστορία ἐκκλησιαστικὴ καὶ μυστικὴ θεωρία") has been preserved in many versions. However, Four main text types can be distinguished, first noted by Frank E. Brightman. Then René Bornert developed this idea.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb
– No

Cemetery
– No

Temple
– No

Shrine
– No

Altar
– No

Devotional marker
– No

Cenotaph

- No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - No
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: The most important manuscripts of Germanos' text are stored, among others, in the Vatican Library, the British Museum, the National Library of France, and the the Ambrosian Library in Milan.
 - Notes: You can find a list of 90 preserved manuscripts of Germanos' text here: <https://pinakes.irht.cnrs.fr/notices/oeuvre/6845/>.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: The text has undergone three main phases of transformation. New paragraphs were included in the original version during the first one, related to types Ba and Bb. Then, branch C developed, characterized by separate textual variants. The summaries Br and Cr have also been extracted from these extensions. The second phase is associated with the emergence of type B, which results from Ba and Bb. Based on the testimony of Anastasius the Librarian, it is believed that this took place at the end of the 9th century. In turn, the third phase extended the B family with numerous interpolations, which changed it to such an extent that it became reasonable to separate the Da and Dp groups. The surviving manuscripts date this more comprehensive recension to the 12th–13th century period.

Reference: Bornert, René. Les commentaires byzantins de la divine liturgie du viie au xve siècle. Archives de l'orient chrétien 9. Paris: L'Institut français d'études byzantines (IFEB), 1966.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– Yes

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The content of the treatise was intended for all believers of the Byzantine Church.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: liturgical commentaries

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: No, the text includes only a commentary.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

- ↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Animal sacrifice?
 - No
 - ↳ Human sacrifice?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text is a commentary on the Christian liturgy. Therefore it is also about the Eucharist, i.e. the body and blood of Christ.
- ↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there material offerings present?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - No
 - ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (i.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: No
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - No
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: On the Divine Liturgy, Bornert, René. Les commentaires byzantins de la divine liturgie du viie au xve siècle. Archives de l'orient chrétien 9. Paris: L'Institut français d'études byzantines (IFEB), 1966.

Reference: On the Divine Liturgy, Brightman, Frank Edward. "The Historia Mystagogica and Other Greek Commentaries on the Byzantine Liturgy". The Journal of Theological Studies 9, no. 34 (January 1, 1908): 248-67. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/jts/os-IX.34.248>.

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Reference: On the Divine Liturgy, Lillie, Ralph-Johannes, Claudia Ludwig, Beate Zielke, and Thomas Pratsch. "Germanos I". Prosopographie der mittelbyzantinischen Zeit Online, 2013. <https://www.degruyter.com/database/PMBZ/entry/PMBZ13412/html>.

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Reference: On the Divine Liturgy, Lamza, Lucian. Patriarch Germanos I. Von Konstantinopel (715-730). Versuch Einer Endgültigen Chronologischen Fixierung Des Lebens Und Wirkens Des Patriarchen. Das Östliche Christentum N.F. 27. Würzburg: Augustinus-Verlag, 1975.

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Reference: On the Divine Liturgy, Beck, Hans-Georg. Kirche Und Theologische Literatur Im Byzantinischen Reich. Byzantisches Handbuch. Im Rahmen Des Handbuchs Der Altertumswissenschaft. II. Teil 1. Band. München: Verlag C. H. Beck, 1959.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Bornert, René. Les commentaires byzantins de la divine liturgie du viie au xve siècle. Archives de l'orient chrétien 9. Paris: L'Institut français d'études byzantines (IFEB), 1966.